

KIMYO INTERNATIONAL UNIVERSITY IN TASHKENT

Journal of digital medicine

<https://medarticle.kiut.uz/>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20662353>

**EFFECTIVENESS OF TRANSCUTANEOUS
ELECTRONEUROSTIMULATION IN THE COMPLEX TREATMENT OF
PATIENTS WITH PARTIAL ADENTIA AND SYMPTOMS OF
TEMPOROMANDIBULAR JOINT DYSFUNCTION**

*Dadabaeva Mukhlisa Ulugbekovna- DSc, Associate Professor of the Department
of Hospital Orthopedic Dentistry of the Tashkent State Medical University*

*Nabiraeva Bakhora Akmalovna- applicant of the Department of Hospital
Orthopedic Dentistry of the Tashkent State Medical University*

Annotation

The aim of the study was to evaluate the effectiveness of transcutaneous electrical nerve stimulation (TENS) in patients with temporomandibular joint (TMJ) dysfunction and partial secondary edentia.

Materials and Methods: To study the muscle relaxation effect of transcutaneous electrical nerve stimulation, we examined 124 patients aged 18 to 70 years. Patients underwent ultra-low-frequency TENS therapy using a J5 myomonitor manufactured by Myotronics. Each session lasted 40 minutes.

Conclusion: Based on the obtained results, increasing the effectiveness of transcutaneous electrical nerve stimulation in the treatment of temporomandibular joint dysfunction in patients with partial edentulism is an effective method for relaxing the masticatory and cervical muscles. This method allows for the determination of the individual physiological position of the mandible when creating a constructive occlusion in patients with partial tooth loss and symptoms of temporomandibular joint dysfunction (TMD). The examination and treatment

protocols for patients with partial tooth loss and symptoms of TMJ achieve positive results in 78% of patients.

Keywords:

transcutaneous electrical nerve stimulation, temporomandibular joint dysfunction, secondary adentia, J5 myomonitor, neuromuscular dentistry.

Introduction

Temporomandibular joint (TMJ) disorders are one of the most pressing issues in modern dentistry due to their high prevalence and diverse clinical manifestations. The complexity of the TMJ's anatomical structure, the variability of its pathological processes, and the wide range of clinical symptoms significantly complicate timely and accurate diagnosis. This study aims to improve the effectiveness of orthopedic treatment for patients with TMJ disorders.

Particular attention was paid to the choice of method for determining the central position of the mandible. Normalizing the spatial relationship of the upper and lower jaws is believed to promote harmonized muscle activity and restore the functional interaction of the TMJ elements. A literature review identified seven different ways to describe the central position of the jaws [1, 2]. Despite differences in interpretation, experts agree on the necessity of a centric position of the mandible for the successful treatment of TMJ disorders.

Determining the centric position of the mandible in TMJ dysfunction is a complex task due to the following factors: occlusal disorders, psychoemotional status, masticatory muscle strain, stretching of the TMJ ligaments, and displacement of the mandible into a forced position [3-5]. In the orthopedic treatment of such patients, accurate determination of the centric position of the mandible is crucial for the design of an occlusal stabilizing device and the normalization of the relationship between the upper and lower jaws, thereby avoiding complications both during and after treatment.

Materials and methods

The main study included 124 individuals, divided into three groups based on the results of a comprehensive clinical and paraclinical examination.

The study group consisted of 35 patients (25 women, 10 men) with partial tooth loss and symptoms of temporomandibular joint dysfunction (TMD). Patients ranged in age from 18 to 70 years, with an average age of 43 +/- 5.5 years. There was a predominance of women, with the largest subgroup comprising women aged 31 to 50 years.

The first control group consisted of 24 patients (11 men, 13 women) aged 18 to 36 years (mean age 28 +/- 6.1 years) with orthognathic malocclusion, no dental defects, and no symptoms or signs of TMJ. These patients did not require treatment and did not undergo the first phase of therapy; however, they voluntarily agreed to participate in the study.

The second control group included 65 patients who had symptoms of TMD but did not undergo treatment during the observation period.

Inclusion criteria for the main group were: age 18 years or older, presence of partial secondary edentia, and clinically confirmed symptoms and signs of TMJ. Exclusion criteria included pregnancy, cancer, and severe somatic pathology.

The study was conducted in accordance with the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki. Approval was received from the Ethics Committee of Tashkent State Medical University (Protocol No. 45 dated March 15, 2023). All patients provided informed consent to participate in the study.

The initial patient examination included collecting complaints and anamnesis in accordance with a developed protocol, which allowed for the identification of both primary and associated symptoms. The data obtained were recorded in an automated registration card. Additionally, patients subjectively assessed the severity and frequency of symptoms on a five-point scale.

Additional examination methods included: study of diagnostic models of the jaws, their installation in the articulator and analysis, production and analysis of diagnostic

photographs of the dental arches, the patient's face, X-ray examination, and functional biometric examination.

During the study, patients underwent ultra-low-frequency transcutaneous electrical nerve stimulation (TENS) using a Myotronics J5 myomonitor (Fig. 1). The stimulation targeted branches of the facial, trigeminal, and accessory cranial nerves. Electrodes were placed on the skin over the V, VII, and XI cranial nerves, in their shallowest locations. Stimulation parameters included an electrical pulse frequency of 1 pulse every 1.5 seconds and an amplitude of 4.5 to 7 mA, which was individually adjusted based on muscle condition. Each session lasted 40 minutes.

Cone beam tomography of the TMJ was performed, with images taken in normal occlusion and with the mouth wide open (Fig. 2). The study included cross-sectional tomograms in three planes at 0.5 mm intervals.

Patient treatment consisted of two main phases. The first phase was aimed at relieving or reducing the severity of TMJ symptoms and normalizing the occlusal relationship of the upper and lower jaws. To achieve these goals, a removable therapeutic and diagnostic mouthguard with an anatomical occlusal surface was used. This phase of treatment lasted up to six months.

Upon completion of this phase, 24 (69.3%) patients underwent orthopedic treatment, including complete reconstruction of the dentition using ceramic crowns, veneers, onlays, bridges, and implant-supported restorations. Prosthetic restorations were performed in the stabilized neuromuscular position of the mandible achieved in the previous phase.

Statistical analysis

Statistical data processing was performed using IBM SPSS Statistics version 26.0. The mean and standard deviation (M +/- SD) were used to describe quantitative variables. The Student's t-test for independent samples and the Mann-Whitney test were used to compare groups, depending on the normal distribution. A significance level of $p < 0.05$ was used to assess the statistical significance of differences.

Research results

The conducted analysis allows us to conclude that, to achieve maximum effectiveness in reducing the symptoms of temporomandibular joint dysfunction (TMD), it is critical to establish constructive occlusion. This occlusion ensures that the electromyographic activity of the temporal muscles during physiological rest of the mandible and during light occlusion of the teeth does not exceed 2.0 μV after transcutaneous electrical nerve stimulation (TENS). Additional alignment of the neuromuscular trajectory with the habitual occlusion contributes to a further reduction in the severity of TMD symptoms.

A comparative analysis of follow-up data from patients in the second control group, who had TMD symptoms but did not undergo treatment, revealed no significant changes in their condition over a six-month period. Specifically, resting temporal muscle activity before relaxation increased by an average of 0.09 \pm 0.02 μV , while after TENS therapy, it increased by 0.5 \pm 0.1 μV . Temporal muscle activity during light occlusion before TENS increased by an average of 0.03 μV , while after TENS, it decreased by 0.12 \pm 0.1 μV .

Based on the data obtained, it can be concluded that cone-beam computed tomography of the temporomandibular joints in patients with clinical manifestations of TMJ reveals bone changes in approximately 30% of cases. The most common of these are deformities of the head of the mandible (in the form of flattening), flattening of the articular tubercle, and the presence of exophytic growths on the articular surfaces.

Discussion

The identified changes indicate a significant prevalence of structural disorders in the temporomandibular joint in this category of patients and emphasize the need to use radiological diagnostic methods in a comprehensive assessment of the condition of the TMJ.

The obtained results are consistent with literature data indicating the high effectiveness of TENS therapy in the complex treatment of patients with TMJ

dysfunction [6]. The use of the J5 myomonitor allows for sufficient muscle relaxation to determine the individual physiological position of the mandible.

Conclusion

1. High prevalence and diversity of TMD symptoms in partial edentulism: patients with partial tooth loss and temporomandibular joint dysfunction (TMD) have an extremely high frequency of pain symptoms (94.2%), accompanied by a wide range of clinical manifestations, such as headaches (85.7%), neck pain (62.5%), auscultatory TMJ phenomena (58.82%), bruxism (54.42%), localized TMJ pain (36.03%) and sleep disorders (32.35%). Moreover, the majority of patients (94%) have multiple symptoms, and 66% have 3 to 7 different symptoms, which emphasizes the complexity of pathogenesis and the need for an integrated approach to diagnosis and treatment.
2. Effectiveness of a two-stage treatment protocol using a diagnostic and therapeutic mouthguard: The developed two-stage treatment protocol, beginning with the use of a removable diagnostic and therapeutic mouthguard, manufactured in the neuromuscular position of the mandible, has demonstrated its effectiveness. This mouthguard performs both a diagnostic function (determining the optimal position of the mandible) and a therapeutic function (normalizing muscle tone, correcting asymmetry, and stabilizing the position of the mandibular heads). A first stage of up to 6 months allows for a significant reduction or elimination of TMJ symptoms.
3. The key role of ultra-low-frequency transcutaneous electrical nerve stimulation (TENS) in stabilizing neuromuscular position: the use of ultra-low-frequency TENS using the J5 myomonitor (Myotronics) to stimulate the branches of the facial, trigeminal, and accessory cranial nerves is an important component of the first stage of treatment. Controlled stimulation parameters (frequency every 1.5 seconds, amplitude of 4.5-7 mA, duration of 40 minutes) promote muscle relaxation and allow for the determination of the individual physiological position of the mandible, necessary for subsequent occlusal stabilization.
4. High success rates of comprehensive rehabilitation: complete orthopedic reconstruction of the dentition (ceramic crowns, veneers, onlays, bridges, implant-

supported restorations) in 69.3% of patients, performed in a stabilized neuromuscular position of the mandible, ensures long-term positive results. Examination and treatment protocols, including the use of TENS and therapeutic and diagnostic mouth guards, achieve positive results in 78% of patients with partial tooth loss and symptoms of TMJ, confirming the high effectiveness of the proposed approach.

List of references

1. Bedoya A., Nieto Z. Centric relation in orthodontics: where do we stand? // J. Clin. Exp. Dent. - 2014. - Vol. 6, N 4. - P. 475-479.
2. Mosby. Diagnosis and treatment of temporomandibular joint dysfunction. - M.: Medical Information Agency, 2016. - 256 p.
3. Soikher M.G. Neuromuscular dentistry. - St. Petersburg: SpetsLit, 2017. - 384 p.
4. Semkin V.A. Orthopedic dentistry. - M.: GEOTAR-Media, 2016. - 432 p.
5. Petrikas I.V., Nikanorov V.I. Dysfunctions of the temporomandibular joint: diagnosis and treatment // Dentistry. - 2018. - V. 97, N 3. - P. 45-51.
6. Olesova V.N. Comprehensive diagnostics of temporomandibular joint dysfunctions // Russian Dental Journal. - 2020. - Vol. 13, N 2. - P. 112-116.
7. Antonik M.M. Computer technologies for complex diagnostics and treatment of patients with dental occlusion pathology complicated by muscular-articular dysfunction: diss. ... Doctor of Medical Sciences: 14.01.14 / Antonik Mikhail Mikhailovich. - M., 2012. - 43 p.
8. Nabiraeva B.A., Dadabaeva M.U. Use of percutaneous neurostimulation in patients with partial edentia due to temporomandibular joint dysfunction // Integrative Dentistry and Maxillofacial Surgery. - 2024. - Vol. 3, N 3. - P. 104-109. DOI: 10.57231/j.idmfs.2024.3.3.012
9. Nabiraeva B.A., Dadabaeva M.U. Frequency of occurrence of symptoms of temporomandibular joint dysfunction // Current issues of orthopedic dentistry and orthodontics: materials of scientific and practical. conf. - Tashkent, 2024. - P. 52-55.

10. Nabiraeva BA Application of transcutaneous neurostimulation in patients with partial adentia in temporomandibular joint dysfunction // European Journal of Modern Medicine and Practice. - 2025. - Vol. 5, N 1. - P. 289-293.